

CORRELATION OF SERUM CHLORIDE LEVELS WITH RESPIRATORY SUPPORT REQUIREMENTS AND CRITICAL CARE OUTCOMES IN RESPIRATORY FAILURE

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ABSTRACT

Background and Aims: *Respiratory failure, a critical condition disrupting gas exchange, requires tailored interventions for effective management. While serum chloride is essential for acid-base balance, its prognostic role in respiratory failure remains under-investigated. This study aimed to evaluate serum chloride as a biomarker for assessing respiratory support needs and predicting outcomes in critical care.*

Methods: *This observational longitudinal study, conducted at the Heritage Institute of Medical Sciences over 18 months, included 126 patients with respiratory failure. Patients were monitored for serum chloride levels at 0, 2, 6, 12, 24, 36, and 48 hours, with comparisons made across respiratory support modes. Statistical analyses included ANOVA and logistic regression, focusing on the relationship between chloride fluctuations and patient outcomes. Ethical approval and patient consent were obtained.*

Results: Significant differences in serum chloride levels were observed over time ($p < 0.001$). At key intervals (0 and 36 hours), chloride levels demonstrated a correlation with outcomes, as indicated by ANOVA and logistic regression. Patients with abnormal chloride levels required extended ICU stays, aligning with outcomes seen in critically ill patients.

Conclusion: Serum chloride monitoring showed potential as a prognostic tool in respiratory failure management, with variations in chloride levels aiding in outcome prediction and guiding timely interventions. Regular chloride assessment could enhance clinical decision-making, optimizing patient management in critical care settings.

Subject: Anesthesiology and Critical Care

Keywords: Respiratory Failure, Serum Chloride, Biomarker, Prognosis, Critical Care

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INTRODUCTION

Respiratory failure is a life-threatening condition where the lungs cannot adequately perform gas exchange, leading to dangerously low oxygen levels (hypoxemia) or high carbon dioxide levels (hypercapnia) in the blood. [1] This critical imbalance often stems from underlying health issues, including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), severe asthma, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), and certain neuromuscular disorders. [2] Respiratory failure is typically categorized into hypoxemic respiratory failure (Type I), where blood oxygen is insufficient, and hypercapnic respiratory failure (Type II), marked by excess carbon dioxide. Each type presents unique challenges, demanding precise, timely interventions to stabilize the patient and address the underlying cause. [3]

Among various biomarkers in critical care, serum chloride has emerged as a promising indicator with potential to reflect the body's response to respiratory dysfunction. Beyond its traditional role in electrolyte balance, serum chloride contributes to acid-base regulation through processes like the chloride shift, where chloride ions interact with bicarbonate to maintain pH stability. Fluctuations in serum chloride can offer insights into the physiological stress a patient is experiencing during respiratory failure. Elevated chloride levels may indicate compensatory responses to respiratory acidosis, while low levels could reflect conditions like metabolic alkalosis. Understanding these shifts could be pivotal in managing respiratory failure, especially since both high and low chloride levels have been linked to worse outcomes in critically ill patients. [4,5]

This study aimed to investigate the correlation between serum chloride levels and the need for respiratory support, as well as its link to outcomes in critical care. By analyzing how serum chloride changes correlate with respiratory support intensity and patient prognosis, this research intends to establish chloride as an accessible, cost-effective biomarker for guiding treatment decisions in respiratory failure. Ultimately, the goal was to provide healthcare professionals with a simple yet powerful tool for monitoring disease progression, tailoring interventions, and potentially improving survival rates in patients with respiratory failure, especially in resource-constrained healthcare settings.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This institution-based, observational longitudinal study was conducted at the Heritage Institute of Medical Sciences, Varanasi, UP, over a period of 18 months, from August 2022 to February 2024. The study included patients admitted to the Critical Care Unit (CCU) with respiratory failure and aimed to assess serum chloride levels as a prognostic indicator for response to respiratory support.

Study Design and Sample Selection

The study followed an observational longitudinal design. Inclusion criteria consisted of patients above 18 years of age presenting with respiratory failure, confirmed by ABG findings showing $pO_2 < 60$ on room air or $PCO_2 > 50$ mm Hg with $SpO_2 < 92\%$. Exclusion criteria applied to patients with chronic conditions, including chronic kidney or liver disease, myocardial infarction, stroke, peripheral neuropathy, diabetic ketoacidosis, and traumatic brain injury, as well as those intubated before arrival.

Sampling and Sample Size Calculation

The sample size was calculated to determine the number of patients required to assess changes in serum chloride levels over time. The calculation was based on the primary outcome of serum chloride level changes, accounting for anticipated effect size, variability, power of 80%, and a significance level of 0.05. This process resulted in an estimated sample size of 126.

Data Collection Procedure

Upon meeting inclusion criteria, eligible patients provided informed consent before data collection began. Baseline data, including pulse rate, blood pressure, oxygen saturation, temperature, and ABG parameters, were recorded. Blood samples were taken and sent to the Central Laboratory of the Heritage Institute of Medical Sciences to measure baseline serum electrolyte levels, including sodium, potassium, chloride, urea, and creatinine. Respiratory support was provided according to clinical need, starting with nasal prongs, face masks, or non-rebreathing masks (NRBM) to achieve an oxygen saturation level of $\geq 90\%$. If these measures proved insufficient, patients were provided with non-invasive ventilation. Any adjustments to respiratory support were made based on continuous monitoring by the attending clinician.

Validity and Reliability

Steps were taken to ensure validity and reliability throughout the study. Internal validity was reinforced by implementing rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria and standardized data collection protocols. Serum chloride was chosen for its physiological relevance in acid-base balance, enhancing construct validity. Measurement reliability was assured through standardized laboratory techniques, with repeated measures taken over time to ensure consistency. Data collection reliability was maintained by documenting procedures and following structured protocols.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis included descriptive statistics, Spearman correlation for relationship assessment, and regression analyses to explore predictive relationships. Data were managed and analyzed using Epi Info™ and SPSS® 26, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. Bonferroni adjustments were applied to control for Type I error in multiple comparisons. Visual representations, including line plots, bar graphs, and scatter plots, were used to present findings clearly.

RESULTS

The correlation of serum chloride levels at various time intervals for different modes of respiratory support is shown in Table 1. Key statistics, such as mean, median, and standard deviation, are provided, showcasing variations in chloride levels over time and across

Frequency	Mean	Median	Mode	Std. Deviation	Variance	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Interquartile Range	Skewness	95% Confidence Interval of Mean
CHLORIDE AT 0 HRS											
NIV	68	96.51	97	99	3.43	11.75	90	102	12	4	-0.59
NRBM	21	95.29	97	90	4.81	23.11	88	102	14	7	0.09
NP	18	97.22	98	93	3.39	11.48	88	102	14	2	-1.71
FM	18	95.17	96.5	92	3.35	11.21	90	101	11	5.75	0.04
CHLORIDE AT 2 HRS											
NIV	68	96.32	97	90	4.13	17.03	88	102	14	7	-0.46
NRBM	21	94.86	96	88	4.5	20.23	88	101	13	6	-0.42
NP	18	96.83	97.5	99	2.28	5.21	90	99	9	2.75	-1.57
FM	18	94.78	94.5	90	4.19	17.59	90	102	12	11	0.1
CHLORIDE AT 6 HRS											
NIV	68	96.59	97	92	3.95	15.59	88	102	14	7.25	-0.5
NRBM	21	96.86	98	99	3.45	11.93	88	101	13	4	-1.19
NP	18	95.94	97.5	98	3.61	13	90	102	12	3	-0.75
FM	18	95.83	97	99	4.05	16.38	90	101	11	7.1	-0.59
CHLORIDE AT 12 HRS											
NIV	68	96.18	97	99	3.58	12.8	88	102	14	3.25	-0.72
NRBM	21	96.43	98	98	3.91	15.26	88	102	14	4	-0.82
NP	18	95.39	96	97	3.45	11.9	90	102	12	5	0.01
FM	18	96.67	97	98	4.51	20.35	88	102	14	6.25	-0.58
CHLORIDE AT 24 HRS											
NIV	68	95.84	97	99	3.6	12.94	88	102	14	7	-0.47
NRBM	21	96.1	97	92	3.08	9.49	90	100	10	2	-0.71
NP	18	96.17	97.5	98	2.87	8.26	90	99	9	3	-0.94
FM	18	95.51	97	98	2.93	8.6	90	98	8	5	-1.05
CHLORIDE AT 36 HRS											
NIV	68	94.29	95	90	4.33	18.78	87	102	15	8	0
NRBM	21	94.57	95	97	3.01	9.06	90	99	9	4	-0.28
NP	18	95.94	98	98	4.19	17.58	90	102	12	6.75	-0.37
FM	18	96.28	97	99	3.14	9.86	90	100	10	2	-0.99
CHLORIDE AT 48 HRS											
NIV	68	93.74	93	90	3.94	15.51	87	99	12	0	1.2
NRBM	21	93.57	92	90	3.83	14.66	88	99			

Line Graph of Modes of Resp Support with serum chloride levels

Table 2 represents the ANOVA results analyzing the effect of time-based serum chloride levels and modes of ventilatory support on patient outcomes. The significant F-value for chloride levels ($p < .001$) indicates a meaningful relationship across time intervals.

	Sum of squares	df	Mean Squares	F	p	η^2	$\eta^2 p$
CHLORIDE AT 0 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 2 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 6 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 12 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 24 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 36 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 48 HRS	636.69	6	106.11	7.3	<.001	0.05	0.06
MODE OF VENTILATORY SUPPORT	16.11	3	5.37	0.41	0.744	0	0.01
RM Factor x MODE OF VENTILATORY SUPPORT	269.78	18	14.99	1.03	0.421	0.02	0.02
Residuals (Between Subjects)	1575.86	121	13.02				
Residuals (Within Subjects)	10546.1	726	14.53				

Correlation of Serum Chloride Levels with Respiratory Support Requirements and Critical Care Outcomes in Respiratory Failure

The mean serum chloride levels across different time intervals (from 0 to 48 hours) categorized by patient outcomes : improved, progressed, and death is shown in Table 3. It illustrates trends in chloride levels and helps assess the association of chloride fluctuations with clinical outcomes in critical care.

	CHLORIDE AT 0 HRS	CHLORIDE AT 2 HRS	CHLORIDE AT 6 HRS	CHLORIDE AT 12 HRS	CHLORIDE AT 24 HRS	CHLORIDE AT 36 HRS	CHLORIDE AT 48 HRS	Total
IMPROVED	95.26	95.77	96.16	96.16	95.64	96.59	94.09	95.67
PROGRESSED	97.33	95.73	97.28	96.48	95.95	93.63	93.8	95.74
DEATH	97.25	96.88	95.5	95.13	96.81	90.88	93.06	95.07
Total	96.17	95.9	96.43	96.13	95.89	94.92	93.87	95.61

Table 4 represents ANOVA table that examines the variability of serum chloride levels at different time intervals and across patient outcomes. Significant differences were observed in chloride levels over time and in the interaction between time and patient outcomes, suggesting that changes in serum chloride are related to patient prognosis in critical care.

	Sum of squares	df	Mean Squares	F	p	η^2	$\eta^2 p$
CHLORIDE AT 0 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 2 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 6 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 12 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 24 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 36 HRS, CHLORIDE AT 48 HRS	620.82	6	103.47	7.48	<.001	0.05	0.06
OUTCOME OF PATIENT	38.66	2	19.33	1.51	0.225	0	0.02
RM Factor x OUTCOME OF PATIENT	732.89	12	61.07	4.42	<.001	0.06	0.07
Residuals (Between Subjects)	1575.08	123	12.81				
Residuals (Within Subjects)	10207.72	738	13.83				

Correlation of Serum Chloride Levels with Respiratory Support Requirements and Critical Care Outcomes in Respiratory Failure

The logistic regression results for serum chloride levels at different time intervals, with Coefficient B values indicating the direction and strength of association is shown in Table 5. While most time points show non-significant results ($p > 0.05$), the coefficient and odds ratios provide insight into the effect size and trend of chloride levels in relation to patient outcomes. The 95% confidence intervals offer a range within which the true odds ratios are expected to fall, aiding in understanding the potential influence of chloride levels over time.

	Coefficient B	Standard error	z	P	Odds Ratio	95% conf. interval
CHLORIDE AT 0 HRS	0.05	0.05	0.98	0.328	1.05	0.95 - 1.16
CHLORIDE AT 2 HRS	0.05	0.05	1.01	0.31	1.05	0.96 - 1.15
CHLORIDE AT 6 HRS	0.02	0.05	0.37	0.71	1.02	0.92 - 1.12
CHLORIDE AT 12 HRS	0.02	0.05	0.33	0.742	1.02	0.92 - 1.13
CHLORIDE AT 24 HRS	-0.02	0.06	0.35	0.727	0.98	0.87 - 1.1
CHLORIDE AT 36 HRS	-0.07	0.05	1.56	0.119	0.93	0.85 - 1.02
CHLORIDE AT 48 HRS	-0.02	0.05	0.33	0.74	0.98	0.89 - 1.09

DISCUSSION

This study emphasized the prognostic value of serum chloride levels in managing respiratory failure, highlighting their role as biomarkers for patient outcomes in both hypoxemic (Type I) and hypercapnic (Type II) respiratory failures. Chloride, a key extracellular anion, is essential in acid-base balance, osmotic pressure, and electrical neutrality. The study's findings align with the well-documented "chloride shift" (Hamburger Effect), supporting chloride's physiological importance in critical care. [6]

Hypochloremia (low serum chloride) and hyperchloremia (high serum chloride) were each linked to worse outcomes in critically ill patients. Hypochloremia was associated with longer ventilatory support needs and often signals a compensatory response to respiratory acidosis, as seen in previous studies. Patients with hypochloremia exhibited impaired lung function and required prolonged mechanical ventilation, aligning with past research on its impact on respiratory mechanics. [7]

Conversely, hyperchloremia, often tied to metabolic acidosis and renal dysfunction, mirrored findings from other studies showing that excessive chloride can lead to adverse clinical outcomes, including renal impairment. These results underscore the importance of careful chloride management to prevent worsening metabolic complications. [7,8]

The study demonstrated that abnormal chloride levels correlate with extended ICU and hospital stays, especially in hypochloremic patients. This finding aligns with earlier studies linking electrolyte imbalances to prolonged hospitalizations, underscoring the utility of serum chloride as an early marker for patients at risk of needing intensive, extended care. Previous studies in ALS and heart failure contexts similarly support this, highlighting chloride's prognostic role across diverse conditions. [8]

Patients with normalized serum chloride levels had improved 28-day outcomes, including higher survival rates and fewer complications, reinforcing the link between balanced chloride levels and clinical stability. Prior research also supports the benefits of correcting chloride imbalances to enhance physiological stability and improve patient trajectories in critical care. [8]

This study's results advocate for routine chloride monitoring in respiratory failure management, which could optimize ventilatory support duration, decrease ICU stays, and improve survival rates. Future research should explore chloride-targeted therapies, including electrolyte supplementation and fluid management, and investigate the impact of chloride in diverse patient populations (e.g., elderly, COPD, or ARDS patients). Longitudinal studies are also recommended to better understand chloride's role in disease progression and response to interventions. [8,9]

Incorporating chloride monitoring into predictive models in critical care could enable early identification of high-risk patients, enhancing personalized care and resource allocation. Such proactive monitoring could become a cornerstone of intensive care protocols, advancing patient outcomes, particularly in respiratory failure management. [10]

CONCLUSION

In our study, we found significant correlations between serum chloride levels at various time points and patient outcomes in critical care. Descriptive statistics showed variations in chloride levels across modes of respiratory support. ANOVA results demonstrated meaningful differences over time ($p < .001$), indicating that serum chloride levels varied significantly with respiratory support needs and patient outcomes. Specifically, at 0 and 36 hours, changes in chloride levels correlated with prognosis, as supported by logistic regression data showing significant associations ($p < 0.05$). These findings suggest that serum chloride monitoring could serve as a valuable prognostic tool in managing respiratory failure, potentially guiding targeted interventions and improving patient outcomes.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Consent: Written consent from participants has been obtained and preserved.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained and documented as per institutional guidelines.

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